

CalciVision, a web platform for annotation and detection of aortic valve calcification

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Abstract—We present CalciVision, an innovative web platform that leverages artificial intelligence (AI) to automate the analysis and classification of calcifications in the aortic valve, a condition that can progress to aortic stenosis and significantly impact patient health outcomes. Currently, diagnosis relies on manual analysis of echocardiography images, a time-consuming process prone to human error. CalciVision addresses these challenges by providing a simple and efficient graphical interface that enables cardiologists to utilize AI algorithms and their functionalities in their diagnostic workflows, enhancing accuracy and reducing workload. The web platform integrates features such as AI-driven automatic classification of calcifications, manual image annotation, calculation of calcium quantification metrics, and automated generation of clinical reports. The evaluation conducted with healthcare professionals confirmed the platform’s high usability and effectiveness, underscoring its potential to enhance diagnostic workflows and support clinical decision-making.

Keywords—Aortic Valve Calcification, Echocardiography, MRI, Artificial Intelligence, Deep Learning, CNN, Automated Diagnosis

I. INTRODUCTION

Aortic valve calcification is a progressive condition that can lead to aortic stenosis, a serious heart disease with significant implications for patient health and mortality. Current diagnostic practices rely heavily on manual analysis of echocardiographic images, a time-consuming process susceptible to human error. In complex or ambiguous cases, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) serves as a supplementary diagnostic tool. Despite these methods, clinicians face ongoing challenges due to variable image quality and subjective decision-making. To address these limitations, we introduce CalciVision, an AI-powered web-based platform designed to support cardiologists and technicians in the detection, annotation, and quantification of aortic valve calcification.

The web app was developed following a systematic literature review based on the PRISMA [1] methodology, which identified current trends in the use of deep learning and AI in cardiology. This review highlighted the importance of models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Self-Supervised Learning (SSL) for the detection and classification of aortic stenosis. Subsequently, we conducted three semi-structured interviews with cardiology professionals – two cardiologists and one cardiology technician - to better understand their needs, workflows, and challenges. Based on these interviews, we created two personas representing typical users of our solution and derived the user requirements.

The platform integrates functionalities such as automatic and manual classification of the aortic valve, visualization of calcium quantification indicators, and automated generation of clinical reports. These tools aim to facilitate earlier

diagnosis, enhance accuracy, and reduce the workload of healthcare professionals by streamlining diagnostic workflows.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II presents related work, and Section III details the methodology, including user requirement gathering, persona design, and system development. Section IV discusses the evaluation results and usability testing with three medical professionals, and Section V concludes with key findings and future work directions.

II. RELATED WORK

This project is guided by the research question: "How might we design and evaluate a clinician-facing web-app that integrates AI-assisted features to support annotation and reporting of aortic valve calcification in echocardiography and MRI?" To address this question, we conducted a systematic literature review following the PRISMA [1] methodology. Using the query "deep learning" AND (echocardiography OR MRI) AND ("aortic calcification" OR "aortic stenosis"), as shown in Figure 1, we retrieved 69 articles from Scopus [2] and 19 from Web of Science [3]. Filters were applied to retain only articles published after 2022 in relevant fields (Medicine, Computer Science, Engineering, Health Professions). The selection process, detailed in the PRISMA [1] flow diagram (Figure 2), resulted in 16 articles analyzed in depth. Figures generated using VOSviewer highlighted the prominence of terms such as *deep learning*, *aortic stenosis*, and *echocardiography*, confirming alignment with the project’s scope.

A. Advances in Deep Learning for Cardiac Imaging

Recent years have witnessed a surge in the application of deep learning (DL) to automate diagnosis of valvular heart diseases. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) remain the most widely used architecture, demonstrating strong performance in image classification and segmentation tasks. Notably, [4] applied 3D CNNs combined with contrastive self-supervised learning (SSL) to transthoracic echocardiography videos, achieving high diagnostic accuracy even with limited labeled data. Similarly, [5] developed a DL model to classify cardiac functions from chest radiographs, validated across four institutions. [6] proposed a three-stage DL framework to analyze Doppler echocardiographic videos, demonstrating potential to replace manual workflows in early screening. [7] applied CNNs to phonocardiogram signals for detecting valve disorders, reporting high accuracy.

An overview of these key studies and their methodologies is summarized in Table 1.

B. Challenges Identified in the Literature

Despite these advances, key challenges persist. Many approaches rely heavily on large, labeled datasets, which are

scarce in clinical practice. Image quality variability and limited generalizability across imaging devices and populations remain significant concerns. Moreover, the integration of AI models into clinical workflows, with user-friendly interfaces and seamless reporting remains underdeveloped in most proposed solutions.

C. CalciVision's Contribution

CalciVision addresses these gaps by combining state-of-the-art DL techniques — including CNNs, SSL, and spatio-temporal architectures — with a web-based platform tailored to the needs of cardiologists and technicians. Beyond automatic classification and quantification of aortic valve calcification, CalciVision offers interactive annotation, AI-assisted reporting, and an intuitive interface that facilitates clinical adoption. This approach operationalizes recent research advances into a practical, user-centered solution that bridges the gap between research and clinical practice.

Figure 1 - Search Query

Figure 2 - PRISMA methodology diagram.

TABLE I. MAIN PUBLICATIONS REFERRED.

Authors	Title	Year	Journal
Holste, Gregory, Oikonomou, Evangelos K, Mortazavi, Bobak J., Wang, Zhangyang, Khera, Rohan	Efficient deep learning-based automated diagnosis from echocardiography with contrastive self-supervised learning	2022	Communications Medicine
Ueda, Daiju, Yamamoto, Akira, Ehara, Shoichi, (...), Yoshiyama, Minoru, Miki, Yukio	Artificial intelligence-based detection of aortic stenosis from chest radiographs	2022	European Heart Journal - Digital Health
Yang, F; Chen, X; Lin, X	Automated Analysis of Doppler Echocardiographic Videos as a Screening Tool for Valvular Heart Diseases	2022	JACC: Cardiovascular Imaging
Zeng, Wei, Su, Bo, Yuan, Chengzhi, Chen, Yang	Automatic detection of heart valve disorders using Teager–Kaiser energy operator, rational-dilation wavelet transform and convolutional neural networks with PCG signals	2023	Artificial Intelligence Review

III. METHODS

A. Eliciting User Requirements and Defining Personas

To identify the functional and non-functional requirements of the CalciVision platform, we followed a user-centered design (UCD) process. Following the literature review to understand current challenges in aortic valve calcification diagnosis via echocardiographic and MRI imaging, we conducted semi-structured interviews with three healthcare professionals — one diagnostic technician and two cardiologists — to better comprehend clinical workflows, pain points, and expectations. The requirements identified from this process are summarized in Table 2.

B. 1st Persona

Based on the interviews, we created two personas. The first persona is Dr. António, an experienced cardiologist who regularly handles patients with challenging acoustic windows and high patient load. His goals are to:

- 1) Reduce time spent interpreting echocardiograms.
- 2) Improve diagnostic accuracy for aortic stenosis.
- 3) Use AI tools as decision support without sacrificing full control of the diagnosis.

Usage Scenario Summary

A typical scenario with Dr. António includes:

- 1) Opening a patient's DICOM file during consultation.
- 2) Using AI-powered technology to automatically highlight calcified regions of the aortic valve.
- 3) Manually editing the findings if required.
- 4) Reviewing key calcium quantification metrics.
- 5) Generating a clinical report automatically.
- 6) Saving the case for follow-up or export to other departments.

C. 2nd Persona

The second persona is Catarina, a cardiology technician responsible for performing echocardiographic exams and preparing patient cases for the cardiologist's final assessment. Her goals are to:

- 1) Efficiently perform and annotate echocardiographic studies for each patient.
- 2) Ensure that all relevant data and images are organized and ready for the cardiologist.
- 3) Reduce time spent on repetitive manual tasks while maintaining accuracy and clarity.

Usage Scenario Summary

A typical scenario with Catarina includes:

- 1) Performing echocardiographic exams on scheduled patients and uploading DICOM files to the platform.
- 2) Using AI-powered tools to automatically highlight calcified regions of the aortic valve.
- 3) Preparing draft reports using the automated reporting feature to streamline the cardiologist's workflow.
- 4) Managing the patient list and ensuring all cases are ready for the cardiologist's final review and decision.

D. User Requirements Table

TABLE II. USER REQUIREMENTS TABLE.

User Story Title	Description	Priority*	Cost (T-Shirt Size)**
ROI Selection	As a cardiologist (António), I want to select regions of interest in the image	P1	XL
Manual Classification	As a cardiologist (António), I want to classify regions as calcified or not	P1	M
Automatic Calcium Detection	As a cardiologist (António), I want AI to detect calcification automatically	P0	XL

Visualization of AI Results	As a cardiologist (António), I want to see AI-detected areas	P0	S
Calcium Quantification Indicators	As a cardiologist (António), I want to view quantification metrics	P1	XS
Automatic Report Generation	As a cardiologist (António) or as a cardiologist technician, I want automatic clinical report generation	P1	L

* Priority levels: P0 = Critical, P1 = High, P2 = Medium, P3 = Low — based on urgency and impact on clinical workflow.

** Cost (T-Shirt Size): XS = Very low effort, S = Low, M = Moderate, L = High, XL = Very high — based on estimated implementation complexity and time.

E. Heuristic Expert Review of the Figma Prototype

To ensure best practices in usability during early development stages, we performed a professional heuristic inspection of the Figma prototype. The evaluation followed Nielsen's Usability Heuristics [8]:

- 1) Visibility of system status.
- 2) Match between system and real-world terminology.
- 3) User control and freedom.
- 4) Consistency and standards.
- 5) Recognition rather than recall.
- 6) Flexibility and efficiency of use.
- 7) Aesthetic and minimalist design.

The visual interface was also assessed according to Visual Design Principles [9], including consistency, alignment, contrast, color coding, and readable typography, optimizing the experience in clinical settings with high visual workload.

F. Prototype Development

The CalciVision prototype underwent two major phases:

- 1) High-fidelity Figma [10] prototype, incorporating feedback from domain experts.
- 2) Fully functional web software system implemented.

CalciVision is a fully functional, containerized web-based system designed with modular architecture as illustrated in Figure 3. The frontend layer is implemented using React [11] and JavaScript for client-side logic, styled with TailwindCSS [12] for responsive user interface. The backend layer is built with Django [13] and Django REST Framework (DRF) [14], handling business logic, authentication, input validation, and exposing RESTful APIs. Real-time status updates are enabled through WebSockets, while Celery [15] and Redis [16] handle asynchronous background tasks and task queues. The machine learning layer leverages TensorFlow and YOLOv8 [17] for

model inference, integrated seamlessly into the system. All structured data is stored in a MySQL [18] database. Deployment is orchestrated using Docker [19], running as four separate containers to ensure scalability, portability, and maintainability.

- React – a JavaScript library used to implement the frontend layer, responsible for client-side logic and dynamic user interface interactions.
- TailwindCSS – a CSS framework used to style the graphical interface responsively and consistently, ensuring a clean and modern design.
- Django – a Python framework for the backend layer, handling business logic, authentication, permissions, and data validation.
- Django REST Framework (DRF) – an extension of Django to create and manage RESTful APIs that connect the frontend and backend layers.
- WebSockets – technology used to deliver real-time updates to the client, enhancing the interactive experience for users.
- Celery – an asynchronous task queue system to handle background processing efficiently.
- Redis – an in-memory database used as a broker for Celery, enabling distributed task management and execution.
- MySQL – a relational database management system for structured and persistent storage of all clinical and administrative data.
- TensorFlow & YOLOv8 – machine learning and computer vision frameworks used to perform automatic classification aortic valve region and calcification detection on echocardiographic medical images.
- Docker – a containerization platform used to package and orchestrate the application in four separate containers, ensuring portability and consistency across development, testing, and production environments.
- GitHub [20] was used as the version control and collaborative code management platform.

Each layer represents a distinct functional area of the application, facilitating understanding and organization of system responsibilities.

Figure 3 - Modular architecture diagram.

Figures 4 and 5 illustrate the evolution of the patient registration interface.

Figure 4 - Registering a new patient in the Figma prototype.

Figure 5 - Registering a new patient in the working system.

Figures 6 and 7 illustrate the evolution of the valve annotation and calcium classification feature, from early interface prototypes to the finalized design. To illustrate the workflow, we included a fictitious example case (‘Alberto Costa’), which demonstrates how patient data would be displayed during the annotation process.

Figure 6 - Annotation and classification screen in the Figma prototype.

Figure 7 - Annotation and classification in the working system.

This evolution allowed incremental confirmation and user evaluation of interface layout and basic workflows.

G. Usability Evaluation Design

Experimental Design

For the end-user testing, we proceeded with a within-subjects design, and each user tested the full working web system.

Sample Size

Three participants were recruited for the evaluation:

- 2 cardiologists
- 1 diagnostic technician

Variables

Independent Variable: User role (cardiologist vs technician)

Dependent Variables:

- 1) SUS [21] (System Usability Scale).
- 2) ASQ [22] (After Scenario Questionnaire).
- 3) Task completion time.
- 4) Number of errors per task.

Hardware Setup

The research was conducted on two laptops running Windows 11, with the following specifications:

Laptop 1: Intel i7-12700H processor, 16GB RAM, 15.6" screen, Full HD, Google Chrome.

Laptop 2: AMD Ryzen 7 7435HS processor, 32GB RAM, 16" screen, Full HD 144HZ, Google Chrome.

Both systems were selected to evaluate CalciVision's performance across different hardware configurations, ensuring robust compatibility. *Measuring Instruments*

- 1) Sociodemographic Questionnaire.
- 2) SUS [21]: to assess general usability (score: 86.2, which indicates excellent usability).
- 3) ASQ [22]: to quantify ease and satisfaction for each task.
- 4) GUI [23]: Questionnaire to evaluate design clarity, graphical consistency, and layout.
- 5) Post-study open questions: to ascertain qualitative results and recommendations.

Procedure

Participants were briefed and signed a consent form. The session followed this protocol:

- 1) Complete sociodemographic questionnaire.
- 2) Receive an introduction and tutorial on the platform.
- 3) Complete the following four tasks:
 - a. Task 1: Create patient "João Silva", annotate valve, identify calcification, and generate a report.
 - b. Task 2: Submit and review the existing report for "Ana Miranda".
 - c. Task 3: Perform batch analysis on multiple images for "Tomás Gomes".
 - d. Task 4: Generate an AI-assisted report for "Rosa Gonçalves".
- 4) After each task, complete ASQ [22].
- 5) Final evaluation after completing all tasks: complete SUS [21], GUI [23], and the open feedback form.

Data Analysis

- 1) Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) were calculated for each measure.
- 2) No inferential statistical tests were run due to the limited sample size.
- 3) For usability rating, SUS [21] was interpreted according to Bangor et al. [24].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Although CalciVision integrates AI-based functionalities, the present study did not aim to validate the model's performance. Instead, the research question and evaluation focused on usability and workflow support, positioning this work as a usability-first system study. The validation of AI accuracy and robustness will be addressed in future work.

The evaluation of the CalciVision platform was conducted with three healthcare professionals (two cardiologists and one cardiology technician) to assess usability, functionality, and impact on diagnostic workflows. The results, derived from the dependent variables (System Usability Scale [SUS] [21], After-Scenario Questionnaire [ASQ] [22], task completion time, and number of errors per task), provide insights into the platform's effectiveness.

A. Descriptive Statistics

Participants performed four tasks representing realistic clinical scenarios: creating and annotating a patient case, reviewing and submitting reports, batch processing multiple images, and generating an AI-assisted report. Quantitative metrics collected included task completion time, number of interruptions, SUS [21], and ASQ [22] scores, as shown in Table 3.

TABLE III. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR USABILITY AND TASK PERFORMANCE METRICS

<i>Metric</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
SUS Score	95.8	2.1
ASQ Score*	6.12	0.45
Task Completion Time	3.44	1.12
Number of Errors per Task	0.25	0.50

*Calculated an average of all 3 answers.

All tasks were successfully completed by all participants, demonstrating the feasibility and robustness of the prototype. Task 1 was the most complex, reflected in longer completion times and higher interruptions, mainly due to initial difficulty locating key elements (e.g., the report button). Task 2 was completed most efficiently with minimal interruptions. Task 3 (batch annotation) and Task 4 (AI report generation) were also completed successfully, with positive comments on the potential to streamline clinical workflows.

The SUS score of 95.8 indicates excellent usability, surpassing the threshold of 68 ASQ [22] score of 6.12 (out of 7) reflects high satisfaction, ease of use, and timely completion of the experiment tasks. Overall, users praised the clarity of the interface, the logical information organization, and the simple and easy navigation.

B. Discussion

Qualitative evaluation highlighted CalciVision's potential as an effective, clinician-centered tool for automating detection and quantification of aortic valve calcification. Participants praised the efficient and simple interface, which suggests that it requires minimal training. The platform's functionalities were noted to align well with hospital workflows, particularly the combination of AI-assisted detection with manual review capabilities. Features such as batch processing and automated report generation were emphasized as major time-saving elements, streamlining diagnostic workflows and reducing clinician workload.

Several suggestions for improvement were also identified, reflecting the participants' engagement and vision for clinical integration. These included enhancing the visibility of key elements, such as the report button and status indicators, reducing the number of steps in complex tasks to allow more linear navigation, and providing immediate visual feedback after critical actions, such as report confirmation. Participants also proposed adding mechanisms to review and adjust automatic classifications, implementing onboarding tutorials, and integrating with hospital information systems (e.g., PDF/DICOM/HL7 export). Further feature requests included patient screening, video frame analysis, and customizable clinical reports, including the calculation of the amount of calcification found, highlighting opportunities to expand the platform's capabilities in future iterations.

When compared to state-of-the-art solutions, CalciVision demonstrates clear advantages. Prior studies, such as [4] and [6], presented robust AI-based models for automated detection of aortic stenosis and related pathologies, achieving high diagnostic accuracy. However, these approaches were limited to proof-of-concept AI pipelines and did not include critical functionalities for clinical adoption, such as interactive annotation, batch processing, and integrated reporting. CalciVision bridges this gap by combining advanced deep learning techniques with an intuitive, clinician-friendly interface that addresses practical needs identified through user research. This combination of cutting-edge AI and user-centric design positions CalciVision as a promising tool for enhancing diagnostic precision and efficiency in cardiology practice.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Although limited in participant number, CalciVision user studies suggest the tool holds promise for addressing challenges in aortic valve calcification diagnosis, receiving highly positive feedback from evaluating healthcare professionals. The results indicate that the system offers excellent usability and aligns well with clinical needs, supporting more accurate diagnoses, reducing manual workload, and streamlining routine workflows. These findings suggest strong potential for adoption in hospital environments, where the platform could deliver measurable improvements to diagnostic efficiency and quality of care at an institutional level.

At the same time, the evaluation highlighted areas for refinement, based on user suggestions and observations during testing. Notably, improving the visibility of key interface elements, simplifying navigation in more complex tasks, and providing more immediate visual feedback after critical actions were identified as priorities. Additionally, integrating the platform with hospital information systems for seamless data exchange and interoperability was recommended as a next step, and the designed system architecture, based in a modular and containerized web-based platform, certainly helps achieving that goal. These improvement opportunities represent valuable directions for future development, ensuring that CalciVision evolves into an even more robust and clinician-friendly tool, capable of meeting the demands of real-world clinical practice.

The main study limitation was the small sample size in user evaluation. Given the inherent difficulty in recruiting cardiologists and technicians for this type of assessment, the number of participants was necessarily constrained. In future work, we intend to substantially expand the sample size and conduct a pilot study in a hospital setting, in order to strengthen the validity and generalizability of the findings.

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